

Conflict, Dissent and Accommodations: Religious imagery in Kṛṣṇa Miśra's *Prabodhacandrodaya*

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I. Introduction

The text *Prabodhacandrodaya*, written by Kṛṣṇa Miśra is an allegorical drama¹. In Sanskrit literature, allegory was never recognized as a distinct genre by Sanskrit writers on literary criticism and poetics.² It was not until recent times, after Western literary categories become known, that writers in the modern Indian languages coined the Sanskrit terms *pratīnāṭaka* (symbolic drama) and *rūpanāṭaka* (metaphorical drama) in order to describe “*Prabodhacandrodaya* (The Rise of Wisdom Moon)” and works resembling it.³

However, the use of allegory was not new in Sanskrit literature. There are fragments of allegory used in the Buddhist literature. There are characters such as *Kīrti* (Fame), *Dhṛti* (Firmness) and *Buddhi* (Wisdom) used by Aśvaghosh in his drama.⁴ There is another allegorical play called *Āgamaḍambara*, written by Jayanta, the author of the *Nyāyamañjarī*, who lived in the ninth century CE.⁵ Kapstein, in the introduction of the translation of the play, says that although Kṛṣṇa Miśra's contribution to Indian literature was not the invention of allegory as such, he may nonetheless be credited with introducing its employment in order to structure an entire literary work from beginning to end.⁶ Kapstein also exposes the problems of allegory as a genre. It takes more effort for a writer to write an allegorical play because he uses one story to tell another which restricts his creativity. He refers to allegory as ‘an unfortunate genre’.⁷

The play *Prabodhacandrodaya* belongs to the second half of the eleventh century CE. The references concerning the Candella ruler Kīrtivarman in the prologue of the play help us in the

¹In the study, the terms ‘drama’ and ‘play’ are interchangeably used.

², Tr. Matthew T. Kapstein, CSL, New York, 2009, p.xxxii.

³Ibid, pp.xxxii-iii.

⁴Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.2 (critical introduction).

⁵Ibid.

⁶Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Matthew T. Kapstein, CSL, New York, 2009, p. xxxiv.

⁷Ibid.

dating of the play.⁸ The text provides the context⁹ which led to the performance of this play at the court of the Candella ruler Kīrtivarman. One of the Candella inscriptions¹⁰ of Kīrtivarman's reign also indicates the same. The language of the play is particularly Sanskrit, but as was the case with many Sanskrit texts of the time, the dialect of *Prākṛit* has been also used.

II. Summary and other details

There are six acts in the play. It has approximately sixty-three characters. Each act has various characters divided into two major parties, led by two kings—king Viveka (Discrimination) and king Mahāmoha (Grand Delusion). The play explicitly provides a context in which it places itself. The context is the restoration of the Candella kingdom during the reign of Kīrtivarman, at whose court the play was performed on the occasion of the latter's victory. The restoration clearly indicates that he may have lost his kingdom or was losing it initially and later recovered it. In the same manner, the story of the play also revolves around the rivalry between two brothers from a family, in which one has taken the possession of the kingdom without sharing it with his brother. Consequently, the deposed brother fights back to regain his share. This is an allegorical play, therefore these two brothers represent two different sets of religious ideologies/philosophies, which are opposed to each other. The subjugated religious ideology/philosophy is asserting to recover from the shadow of the dominant one. Certainly, the issue of recuperation is involved here, i.e., the subservient religious ideology/philosophy was either losing ground or being subordinated and this necessitated a restoration. Furthermore, this recuperation leads to the conflict between these two antagonistic religious ideologies/philosophies, which is the critical theme of the play.

III. Conflict, Dissent and Accommodations: Religious activities in Kṛṣṇa Miśra's *Prabodhacandrodaya*

⁸Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.2-7 (Act I).

⁹The context for the enactment of the play is to celebrate the subjugation of the enemies by the king Kīrtivarman.

Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.4-5 (Act I).

¹⁰E. Hultzsch, Fragmentary Mahobā Inscription of the Candellas, *EI*, I, pp.217-22.

Verse 26 of the inscription records that Kīrtivarman defeated Lakṣmīkarṇa. It is the same Karṇa referred in the prologue of the drama *Prabodhacandrodaya*.

(Mentioned in *EI*, I, p.220) Professor Kielhorn who has studied the Cedi Inscriptions, helps in associating the Karṇa mentioned in the inscription with the Cedi dynasty.

The inscription provides few details, which are similar in the play, too. This helps us in concluding that the composer of the inscription already knew about the existence of the play and borrowed from it. (*EI*, I, p.220).

All these details help us in placing the text in the second half of the eleventh century.

Moving into the details provided in the play, we need a set of questions, which will help us in getting closer to understand the nature of religious activities described in the play. These questions would be:

- a) Which religious sects/philosophies are mentioned in the play?
- b) How they are described in the play? Or what are the specific characteristics of these various religious sects/philosophies?
- c) What are the grounds of their common beliefs or differences, which led to conflict?
- d) As the play was written during the early medieval times and was being performed at the Candella court, what kind of religious imagery it produces of that period at large and the society under the Candellas in particular?

a)

If we look into the play, we get references of various religious sects/philosophies divided into two major contending religious ideologies/philosophies. These two major contending religious ideologies/philosophies in the play are:

Vedic (orthodox) led by king Viveka- *Vedānta*, Non-Vedāntic philosophies (*Mīmāṃsā*, *Nyāya*, *Vaiśeṣika*, and *Sāṅkhya*), Vaiṣṇava, Śaivas (*Paśupatas*), Sauras.

Anti-Vedic (heterodox) led by king Mahāmoha- *Cārvāka*, Buddhist, Jaina, *Kāpālika*

b)

The characteristics of the major religious ideologies/philosophies in the play are given in the form of a contestation between two parties. While this does not restrict them to express their own differences from each other. Therefore, it is necessary that we go into the details of each of these sects/philosophical schools for a comprehensive understanding.

Vedic (orthodox)

Vedānta- In the play, *Advaita Vedānta*¹¹ philosophy of Śaṅkara seems to be the inspiration.¹² But, before going into the details of the *Advaita Vedānta*, it is important to look at the historical genealogy of the *Vedānta*. The literal meaning of the term *Vedānta* is “the final sections of the

¹¹This philosophical school was propounded by Śaṅkara. *Advaita Vedānta* literally means “non-dualist” *Vedānta*. The basic exposition of this philosophical school is that everything which surrounds us including ourselves, in the end, fades into brahman (soul). Brahman is the truth. The universe and us are an illusion due to our ignorance. The only way to remove this illusion is the earnest study of the Upaniṣads. This is the only path for the Vedāntists.

¹²This inference is based on the detailed study of the play. In the end of the play, king Discrimination with the help of *Viṣṇubhakti* unites with the brahman which is Viṣṇu itself. While there is a crucial distinction between Śaṅkara’s *Advaita* and the one mentioned here. The *advaita* of Śaṅkara is of *nirguna* type, while the one mentioned in the play is of *saguna* type.

Veda’’.¹³ It takes its inspiration from the Upaniṣads. While Vedāntic philosophy has a basic literature to adhere, still there are various strands in it, which differ from each other substantially.¹⁴ Still, there are differences between Śaṅkara and Kṛṣṇa Mīśra’s philosophy. Śaṅkara’s attitude towards other religious sects is exclusive and restrictive in nature. As William Halbfass has commented:¹⁵

Śaṅkara’s approach to the problem of religious plurality is restrictive and limited in nature. Unlike later thinkers of the Advaita Vedānta tradition, Śaṅkara is not depicting Vedānta to be inclusive concerning other religious or philosophical teachings.

But this is not the case with Kṛṣṇa Mīśra’s *Prabodhacandrodaya*. This could be considered to be the first work of its kind to express an inclusive vision of *Advaita Vedānta*.¹⁶ The play provides a “big-tent” view of the *Vedānta*, not as one sect or school among others, but as the culmination of a wide range of devotional sects and philosophical schools.¹⁷ In the works of Śaṅkara, there is hardly any mention of Vaiṣṇavism or *bhakti*.¹⁸ However, in the play, the element of *bhakti* is very crucial. It is through *bhakti* (*viṣṇubhakti*) that man attains knowledge, which further helps him realise his identity (union) with Viṣṇu.¹⁹

Non-Vedāntic philosophies- The non-Vedāntic philosophies mentioned in the play are-- *Mīmāṃsā*, *Saṅkhya*, *Nyāya*, *Tarkavidyā* (*Vaiśeṣika*), *Yajñavidyā* etc. They all are particularly discussed through the experience of *Upaniṣad* in the play, as she looks for shelter under the tutelage of these philosophies.²⁰ None of them accepts her. In the end, she has to run away from them for saving herself as they find her philosophy of liberation by the annihilation of Universe close to atheism.²¹ The best difference brought through *Upaniṣad* between *Vedānta* and non-Vedāntic philosophies is related with the ways to attain the happiness or highest happiness (bliss). In case of *Vedānta*, it is *Jñāna*, while in the mentioned non-Vedāntic philosophies it is *Karman*. This distinction was not so smooth and straightforward because *Advaita Vedānta* of Śaṅkara focuses on *Jñāna*, but still it does not refute the importance of *Karman* because it has been part of Vedic religious philosophy.²² For Śaṅkara, *Karman* provides the preparatory ground for *Jñāna*.²³ In the play too, the relationship between *Vedānta* and non-Vedānta philosophies is not very straightforward.

13Karl H. Potter (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Indian Philosophies* (vol.iii), p.3.

14Ibid, pp.3-4.

15(Mentioned in) Michael Allen, ‘Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Saṅkalpasūryodaya’, *The Journal of Hindu Studies*, 9, 2016, p.288.

16Ibid.

17Ibid.

18Kṛṣṇa Mīśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.12 (Intro).

19 Ibid.

20Kṛṣṇa Mīśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.151-165 (Act VI).

21Ibid, p.165 (Act VI)

22Manilal N. Dvivedi, ‘The Advaita Philosophy of Śaṅkara’, 2, *WZKM*, 1888, p.99.

23Ibid.

Vaiṣṇava, Śaivas (Paśupatas) and Sauras- In the play *Viṣṇubhakti* (Devotion to Viṣṇu) helps the devotee in his union with *Viṣṇu*. The union of *Puruṣa* with *Viṣṇu* is described in the play intelligibly in one of the verses.

Mohāndhakāramvadhūya vikalpanidrā

Munmathya Koapyajani Bodhatuṣāraraśmih.

Śradhhāvivekamatiśāntiyamādiken

*Viśvātmakaḥ sfurati viṣṇurahaṁ sa eṣaḥ.*²⁴

[After shaking off the darkness of delusion, after throwing off the sleep of error, a cool ray of Awakening has been born. I am that Viṣṇu who becomes manifest as the Universal Self through faith, discrimination, reason, peace, self-restraint etc.]

Further in another verse, we get reference about the role played by *Viṣṇubhakti* in this union.

*Sarvathā kṛtakṛtyoasmi bhagvatyā viṣṇubhakteḥ prāsādāt.*²⁵

[With the help of Devotion to Viṣṇu, I have been able to achieve what is to be achieved.]

While the play gives primacy to the *Vaiṣṇava Vedānta* tradition, even though the *Śaiva* tradition has not been ignored in the play. Even in the opening verse of the play, we get a reference about the worship of *Śiva*.²⁶ Further in another instance, we get a reference about *Śaiva* and *Paśupatas* in the second act of the play through the supporters of king *Mahāmoha*. But here they are referred as animal-natured (*paśavaḥ pāṣaṅdhāḥ*) and even just by conversing with them, people go to hell.²⁷

About Sauras, we do not get many references in the play. The *Sauras*, were not very influential during the time the play was composed. Even today, their presence is negligible to a certain extent and they are a small sect in some parts of central and southern India whose special object of the worship is the sun, *Sūrya*.²⁸

Anti-Vedic (heterodox)

***Cārvāka* (Materialists)**-The philosophy of the *Cārvāka* is presented in intrepid manner in the play. Various views of *Cārvāka* from the play could be summed up in the following manner:²⁹

-They are very critical of the Vedic religious philosophy. They call these believers (*āstikas*) ignorant as they believe in the concept of the soul separate from the body, which enjoys rewards in netherworld. As per materialists it is so absurd that these believers believe in the existence of a thing, which does not exist at all.

²⁴Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.170 (Act VI).

²⁵Ibid.

²⁶Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.2-3 (Act I).

²⁷Ibid, pp.28-29 (Act II).

²⁸Ibid, p.40 (Intro).

²⁹Ibid, pp.40-45 (Act II).

-As per materialists, only means of pursuing knowledge is the perception.

-They call the Vedas a work of cheats. The only real knowledge is statecraft including agriculture and trade.

-They are also critical of various Vedic sacrifices and rituals.

-Discussing the hardships of ascetics (*bṛahaspati*), who have renounced the world, the materialists say that these ascetics are deceived by the Vedas. They also refer them as human animals, who are being foolish. Invoking the appearance of an ascetic is itself a marker of femininity and foolishness for the materialists.

Buddhist, Jaina and Kāpālika- In the third act³⁰ of the play, all of them together are shown to be engaged in an interesting debate. On the one hand they ridicule each other's religious ideas, while on the other, they stand on a common ground against Vedic religions. While ridiculing each other, they use very philistine language. For example:³¹

Bhikṣu- Āḥ pāpa piśācākrite, kimevaṃ pralapasi?

Mendicant- (*Angrily*) Oh sinner, you who look like an evil spirit, what do you prattle?

In the above statement, this is how a Buddhist addresses to a Jaina. There are many more examples of this kind.

Now let us move on to each of these religious sects and take a closer look at them—what they have to say about their own religious ideology particularly?

As per the Buddhists³², the idea of existence is illusionary and momentary. The idea of self is also an illusion. There is no such religion, where there is enjoyment as well as liberation, except Buddhism. Any person will attain liberation, when he will be able to free himself from all kinds of desires (*vāsanās*).

The teachings of Jainas³³ claim that the self could be known through the service of sages (Jaina sages). One should give respect, food and shelter to the sages. They even go on to say that people in the need of liberation should not feel jealous even when the sages are enjoying their wives. In Jaina tradition, the knowledge of astrology is considered to be of relevance in the play. Jaina also considers “non-injury” to be the highest virtue.³⁴

The *Kāpālikas*³⁵ are referred as *Somasidhhānta* in the play. The character named *Kāpālika* in the play introduces himself as someone who wears garland of human bones as part of his attire, lives in the cremation ground and eats out of a human skull. Going into the details of the

30Ibid, pp.66-91 (Act III).

31Kṛṣṇa Mīśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.70 (Act III).

32Ibid, pp.68-73 (Act III).

33Jaina in the play is referred as ‘Digambara’ and ‘Kṣapaṇaka’.

Kṛṣṇa Mīśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.66-67, 74-75 (Act III).

34Ibid, p.79 (Act III).

35Ibid, pp.75-91 (Act III).

rituals, they (*kāpālikas*) are referred as offering human flesh into the oblation of fire. Lord *Mahābhairava* is the god worshipped by the *Kāpālikas*. Role of pleasure is crucial in their world. Drinking alcohol, enjoying women etc. are some of the other activities being followed by the *Kāpālikas*. Luring through these activities, *Kāpālika* in the play is shown to bring Buddhist and Jaina into his fold.

c)

We have already seen how various religious sects are described in the play. Now, we come to the question of the common grounds of consensus and differences among these sects which led them to form themselves into two opposite religious ideologies/philosophies. These grounds of consensus and differences could be understood in the following ways:

-The tussle for increasing the sphere of influence.

-The need of an alliance: orthodox traditions versus heterodox traditions.

-Inclusivism and Exclusivism: A mutable reality.

The tussle for increasing the sphere of influence- The tussle between orthodox and heterodox traditions is very evident in the play. The heterodox traditions are shown to be in the dominant position. And, this is the cause of concern among the orthodox religious section. This concern of orthodox traditions necessitates them to restore their lost position. How this could be done? This further explains the formation of the alliances.

The need of an alliance: orthodox traditions versus heterodox traditions- In the play, *Vedānta* tradition leads the alliance of orthodox (Vedic) religious ideologies/philosophies. One aspect of this alliance lies in the concept of *āstika/nāstika*.³⁶ The common unifying factor among the orthodox (*Vedic*) religious ideologies/philosophies is their faith in the *Vedas* and ideas concerning soul and afterlife. While the concept of *nāstika* is applied to the followers of *Cārvāka*, who say “there is no” soul and therefore no life after death.³⁷ Later in the play, the term is expanded to include all schools that reject the authority of the *Vedas* and these schools (Jaina, Buddhist, *Cārvāka* and *Somasidhhānta*) form the group of heterodox traditions.³⁸

Further, the alliance among the orthodox traditions could be understood in two forms: a complete inclusivism with respect to the various devotional sects (*Vaiṣṇava* and *Śaiva*) and a temporary inclusivism with respect to the Brahminical *darśanas* (non-Vedāntic philosophies).³⁹ As per the author of the play, devotional sects such as *Vaiṣṇava* and *Śaiva* are closer to Vedāntic religious philosophy because they are based on revelations unlike Brahminical philosophies which are based on reasoning (*tarkavidyā*).⁴⁰ In the play, Sacred Lore (*Upaniṣad*) has been shown to be mistreated by these various Brahminical philosophies. They ridicule her and even try to kill her. Therefore, complete inclusivism has been adopted

36Michael Allen, 'Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Saṃkalpasūryodaya', *The Journal of Hindu Studies*, 9, 2016, p.276.

37Ibid.

38Ibid.

39Ibid, p.279.

40Ibid, pp.278-79.

towards the devotional sects (Vaiṣṇava, Śaiva), while temporary inclusivism towards the brahmanical philosophical schools.⁴¹ The heterodox traditions have been excluded from the purview of *Vedānta* religious philosophy altogether.

Inclusivism and Exclusivism: A mutable reality- In Hinduism, there always has been an ability to absorb potentially schismatic developments.⁴² In one of her essays, while talking about heresy, Doniger has shown how the idea of heresy and heretics in Hinduism has been dynamic. At one place in her essay, for asserting her arguments, she quotes the argument of Louis Renou, “It is quite difficult in India to be completely heretical.”⁴³ In her essay, she talks about two levels of heresy in Hinduism—one is referred to as “orthodox heresies” and another one is referred to as “sectarian heresies”.⁴⁴ The orthodox heresies include those sects which at least pay lip service to the Vedas. This includes *Kāpālika*, *Kaula* and *Paśupatas* sects of Śaivism and the *Pāñcarātra* and *Sāhajiyā* sects of Vaiṣṇavism. While Buddhist, Jaina and Sikhs deny the authority of the Vedas altogether, therefore, they are considered to be completely heretical. The sectarian heresies include those sects which emanate from the orthodox heresies, but follow certain rituals, which are completely antagonistic to Vedic religion. The best example of this kind is the *Kāpālika*. But they are still kept into Hindu fold and in Sanskrit plays, they are shown detesting Buddhists and Jainas. Further, in her essay, she has studied various texts concerning the idea of heresies in Hinduism and it is fairly evident from her essay that the idea of heresies has been dynamic.

Keeping these arguments in the background, if we look into the question of inclusivism and exclusivism concerning *Vedānta*, it could be assumed that the alliance shown in the play was not a standard or universal model to be followed. It means that the idea of whom to include or exclude under the big-tent of *Vedānta* was not monolithic. An important study by Michael Allen helps us in understanding the issue in a better manner. In his study, Michael Allen goes through two plays *Prabodhacandrodaya* by Kṛṣṇa Mīśra and *Samkalpasūryodaya* by Veṅkaṭanātha (also referred as Vedānta Deśika). First play belongs to the second half of the eleventh century CE while the latter one belongs to the second half of the thirteenth or early fourteenth century CE. The play *Prabodhacandrodaya* being older inspired Vedānta Deśika to write the play *Samkalpasūryodaya* using the same allegorical framework and characters. But the crucial difference in both the plays is about the viewpoints from which they are written. The *Prabodhacandrodaya* is written from the viewpoint of *Advaita Vedānta* of Śaṅkara, while *Samkalpasūryodaya* is written from the viewpoint of *Viśiṣṭādvaita Vedānta* of Rāmānuja.⁴⁵ But still, both viewpoints come under the “big-tent” of *Vedānta*. If we look into the play closely, we find that the orthodox religious sects mentioned in the *Vedānta* of *Prabodhacandrodaya*

41Ibid, p.279.

42 Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, *History of Religions*, 10, 1971, p.271.

43(Mentioned in) Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, *History of Religions*, 10, 1971, p.271.

44Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, *History of Religions*, 10, 1971, p.273.

45Michael Allen, ‘Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Samkalpasūryodaya’, *The Journal of Hindu Studies*, 9, 2016, pp.273-297.

turns out to be heretical in the play *Samkalpasūryodaya*. The difference between Kṛṣṇa Miśra's inclusivism and Deśika's exclusivism can be seen in the following tables.⁴⁶

Prabodhacandrodaya: Vedāntic Inclusivism

Samkalpasūryodaya: Vedāntic Exclusivism

From the above details in the table, it is sufficiently clear that the relationship between orthodox and heterodox religious sects was mutable in terms of inclusion and exclusion of various sects in the *Vedānta* traditions.

d)

If we look into the details of religious activities prominent during the early medieval period, we find the evidences of Purāṇic religions (*Śaiva* and *Vaiṣṇava*) dominating the religious sphere. The presence of the heterodox traditions also could be seen, but they are limited to certain geographic quarters. Under the Candellas, it seems that heterodox traditions (i.e. Buddhism, Jainism, *Cārvāka* etc.) were on the rise and this necessitated some action on the part of the Purāṇic religious sects (*Śaivism*, *Vaiṣṇavism* etc.). But what needs to be done and how? —is another important question that needs to be answered.

Advaita Vedānta philosophy is the core theme in the play around which all the other religious sects and the philosophies try to come to terms with. It is because the *Advaita Vedānta* provides the necessary unifying force for the Purāṇic religions for countering the increasing influence of the heterodox traditions. How it does so? It helps Purāṇic religions in establishing alliances with various religious sects who are anywhere close to accepting the supremacy of the Vedas. Even these alliances are not of permanent kind. They are strategic and tactical. Their requirement ends, when the requisite objective is fulfilled.

Why *Advaita Vedānta*? The rationale behind choosing the *Advaita Vedānta* by the Purāṇic religions in countering heterodox traditions could have been the increasing influence of *Advaita vedāntins* in the region held by the Candella rulers. The Vedānticisation of Śaivas in South India is another example of this kind, where Purāṇic religions (*Śaivas*, *Vaiṣṇavas* etc.) structured their theology around the Upaniṣadic (Vedāntic) philosophy as it was gaining momentum in the region between the thirteenth to sixteenth centuries.

1 In the study, the terms 'drama' and 'play' are interchangeably used.

2 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Matthew T. Kapstein, CSL, New York, 2009, p.xxxii.

3 Ibid, pp.xxxii-iii.

4 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.2 (critical introduction).

5 Ibid.

6 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Matthew T. Kapstein, CSL, New York, 2009, p. xxxiv.

7 Ibid.

8 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.2-7 (Act I).

9 The context for the enactment of the play is to celebrate the subjugation of the enemies by the king Kīrtivarman. Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.4-5 (Act I).

10 E. Hultzsch, *Fragmentary Mahobā Inscription of the Candellas*, EI, I, pp.217-22.

Verse 26 of the inscription records that Kīrtivarman defeated Lakṣmīkaṛṇa. It is the same Kaṛṇa referred in the prologue of the drama Prabodhacandrodaya.

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All these details help us in placing the text in the second half of the eleventh century.

11 This philosophical school was propounded by Śaṅkara. Advaita Vedānta literally means “non-dualist” Vedānta. The basic exposition of this philosophical school is that everything which surrounds us including ourselves, in the end, fades into brahman (soul). Brahman is the truth. The universe and us are an illusion due to our ignorance. The only way to remove this illusion is the earnest study of the Upaniṣads. This is the only path for the Vedāntists.

12 This inference is based on the detailed study of the play. In the end of the play, king Discrimination with the help of Viṣṇubhakti unites with the brahman which is Viṣṇu itself. While there is a crucial distinction between Śaṅkara’s Advaita and the one mentioned here. The advaita of Śaṅkara is of nirguṇa type, while the one mentioned in the play is of saṅguṇa type.

13 Karl H. Potter (ed.), Encyclopedia of Indian Philosophies (vol.iii), p.3.

14 Ibid, pp.3-4.

15 (Mentioned in) Michael Allen, ‘Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Saṃkalpasūryodaya’, The Journal of Hindu Studies, 9, 2016, p.288.

16 Ibid., 17 Ibid.

18 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.12 (Intro), 19 Ibid.

20 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.151-165 (Act VI).

21 Ibid, p.165 (Act VI) 22 Manilal N. Dvivedi, ‘The Advaita Philosophy of Śaṅkara’, 2, WZKM, 1888, p.99. 23 Ibid.

24 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.170 (Act VI). 25 Ibid.

26 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.2-3 (Act I). 27 Ibid, pp.28-29 (Act II). 28 Ibid, p.40 (Intro).

29 Ibid, pp.40-45 (Act II). 30 Ibid, pp.66-91 (Act III). 31 Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, p.70 (Act III). 32 Ibid, pp.68-73 (Act III).

33 Jaina in the play is referred as ‘Digambara’ and ‘Kṣapaṇaka’. Kṛṣṇa Miśra, Prabodhacandrodaya, Tr. Sita K. Nambiar, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1998, pp.66-67, 74-75 (Act III).

34 Ibid, p.79 (Act III). 35 Ibid, pp.75-91 (Act III).

36 Michael Allen, ‘Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Saṃkalpasūryodaya’, The Journal of Hindu Studies, 9, 2016, p.276.

37 Ibid. 38 Ibid. 39 Ibid, p.279. 40 Ibid, pp.278-79. 41 Ibid, p.279.

42 Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, History of Religions, 10, 1971, p.271.

43 (Mentioned in) Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, History of Religions, 10, 1971, p.271.

44 Wendy Doniger, ‘The Origin of Heresy in Hindu Mythology’, History of Religions, 10, 1971, p.273.

45 Michael Allen, ‘Dueling Dramas, Dueling Doxographies: The Prabodhacandrodaya and Saṃkalpasūryodaya’, The Journal of Hindu Studies, 9, 2016, pp.273-297. 46 Ibid, p.282.

47 Elaine M. Fisher, ‘Remaking South Indian Śaivism: Greater Śaiva Advaita and the Legacy of the Śaktiviśiṣṭādvaita Vīraśaiva Tradition’, International Journal of Hindu Studies, 21 (3), 2017, pp.319-344